

FEATURES OF FORMATION AND FUNCTIONING OF ABBREVIATIONS IN RUSSIAN, UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The article examines the process of formation of abbreviations of military terminology, their morphological structure and the specifics of use in various language contexts. The features of the formation and functioning of military abbreviations in the Russian and Uzbek languages are analyzed, as well as their comparison with the English language. Particular attention is paid to the similarities and differences in the formation and use of abbreviations between these languages, as well as their role in linguistic communication, especially in the context of military affairs. The results of the study may be useful for linguists, translators and anyone interested in linguistic dynamics and interlingual aspects of communication, especially in the military sphere.*

Keywords: *abbreviation, military terminology, Russian language, Uzbek language, English language, formation of abbreviations, functioning of abbreviations, specialized vocabulary.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the armed forces are one of the most important social institutions in most countries of the world. In view of the military-political contacts between the Russian Federation and NATO member states, as well as the continuous development of the armed forces, the renewal and modification of the technical component and weapons, changes in military directives, orders, charters or other documents, it becomes necessary to study military discourse and translate military texts. Military translation is a separate linguistic discipline due to the high requirements for the quality and accuracy of translation, errors in which, at best, will lead to arbitrary and subjective interpretation of the text and misunderstandings during negotiations, and at worst, they can cost someone their life or entail serious material costs. It requires an impeccable command of not only foreign military terminology, but also adequate Russian and Uzbek military terminology, which is regularly updated. In addition, the translator needs to have deep knowledge of a linguistic and cultural nature, since the approach to military affairs in different countries has significant differences, which is manifested both in the structure of military regulations and in the style of presenting the material. The relevance of the work is also due to the practical assistance in the activities of military translators and general translators, who often come across unfamiliar abbreviations, military abbreviations and, in general, military vocabulary [4, 81].

From the point of view of word formation, abbreviation is a topical subject of research, since the question of whether to consider it one of the ways to form new words is still being discussed. Since abbreviations as a new type of words enriched the system of lexemes of the language, but, however, did not lead to the emergence of any non-lexical, typologically new units, nor did they lead to the complication of the language structure [2,62].

Due to the fact that each language has a limited number of root elements and affixes, today, together with traditional methods of word formation (word production and word formation), such methods of vocabulary replenishment as semantic word formation, borrowing and abbreviation

play an increasingly important role. According to the definition, abbreviations are nouns that consist of truncated segments of words that are part of a synonymous phrase, the supporting component of which cannot be a whole, untruncated word. In this case, the special advantage of abbreviation is the creation of new root words and root elements. It should also be noted that word formation by abbreviation is possible in conjunction with other ways of replenishing the vocabulary. In addition, the language resorts to abbreviations only when they are linguistically more appropriate than in other ways.

A military term should be considered as "a stable unit of a synthetic or analytical nomination assigned to the corresponding concept in the conceptual and functional system of a certain sphere of the military profession in the meaning regulated by its definition." Word formation, in turn, is an integral part of derivational onomasiology, namely the section of secondary nomination, which, together with primary nomination, is studied within the framework of the science of naming known fragments of reality using linguistic means. Derivation is the derivation of some units from others according to certain rules.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Korovushkin, V.P. A Military vocabulary can be divided into military terminology, which includes concepts related to the military sphere, and military-technical terminology, including scientific and technical terms, as well as slang words and phrases that are synonymous with established military terms and are used exclusively in the oral speech of military personnel [10, 86].

In the scientific literature, the terms "abbreviation" and "contraction" are often used as synonyms. According to the famous linguist Sudzilovsky G.A., the term "abbreviation" must be used in the broad sense of the word, and it is any abbreviated version of the spelling and pronunciation of a word (term) or phrase - regardless of its structure and the nature of the resulting unit [14, 182]. According to Bankevich V.V, the terms "abbreviation" and "contraction" as synonyms [5, 113]. It must be emphasized that some linguists Vocabulary of military and technical materials is characterized by the use of a large number of abbreviations. Abbreviation is to ensure the transfer of the maximum amount of information (semantic content) with minimal use of the material shell of the language (sound shell and graphic form), that is, to increase the effectiveness of the communicative function of the language.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Since the abbreviation actively interacts with other ways of word formation. Consider the ways of forming new words using traditional word-formation methods:

- word formation: RAF (Royal Air Force) - Rafer - "a soldier of the British Air Force"; RAND (Research and Development Corporation) - RANDster - "an employee of the RAND Corporation"; morphologically complicated cases are possible, for example: UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) - Unescan - "belonging to UNESCO";

- word combinations: MATS (military Air Transport Service) + man - MATSman - "military air transport service soldier";

- conversions: RAF (Royal Air Force) - to raff - "subject to attack from the air"; PX (Post Exchange) - to PX - "buy something in the store of the military trade service.

In addition, abbreviation is often combined with another way of word formation. With the help of the joint action of abbreviation and suffixation, for example, the words are formed: blackie (blacksmith - black + ie) - blacksmith", brickie (bricklayer> brick + fie) - "mason", postie (postman> post + ie) - "postman". In these cases, special abbreviated morphemes appear (-black-, -brick-, -post-), which only formally coincide with the root morphemes -black-, -brick-, -post- that already existed in English.

Linguists have developed rules for compiling complex abbreviated lexical units from standard abbreviated components. The most successful initial abbreviations are beginning to be used as "samples" to create new abbreviations, which also contributes to the typification of abbreviations. The most important impetus for the development of abbreviation was the discovery and widespread use of correlative acronyms - initial abbreviations that have the phonetic structure of ordinary words [4, 83].

Abbreviation as word formation is a complex and rather extensive phenomenon. The relevance of abbreviation lies in the need to name new concepts and objects. The expediency is the creation of extremely economical and semantically capacious nominative units.

The abbreviation method of word formation is the most subjective and, perhaps, the most artificial among all known methods. This is due to numerous features of abbreviation: trial and error when creating names, variability and occasionality, intensity of diachronic changes, susceptibility to regulation, weak national fixation and free permeability, etc.

Abbreviations and abbreviations are considered productive ways of word formation, both in modern English and in Russian. Compound words, which are formed by adding the initial parts or syllables of words, as well as alphabetic abbreviations, as a more convenient form of complex terms for written communication, have received predominant distribution. In general, abbreviations and abbreviations are more widespread in English than in Russian.

The undeniable fact that abbreviation and abbreviation are the most productive in recent decades and regular ways of forming lexical units means the language's desire to save language efforts, and also indicates its rationalization.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Features of the formation and functioning of abbreviations in the Russian language using the example of military abbreviations are an important aspect of the study of the language and its specifics. Military abbreviations are shortened forms of words and expressions used in military terminology to designate various concepts, organizations, military units, etc. [16, 549].

One of the features of the formation of abbreviations in the Russian language is the use of the first letters of words or phrases that form an abbreviated form. For example, the abbreviation "Air Force" is derived from the phrase "Air Force", where each word is represented by the first letter. This method of forming abbreviations allows you to shorten long and complex phrases, making them more convenient for use in speech and writing [12, 484].

Another feature of the formation of abbreviations is the use of periods between letters. For example, the abbreviation "SVD" is derived from the phrase "Dragunov sniper rifle." The dots between the letters help separate them and indicate that this is an acronym and not just a collection of letters.

The functioning of abbreviations in Russian also has its own characteristics. First, abbreviations are often used in specialized vocabulary, such as military terminology. They help reduce time and effort in communication between specialists and make military terms easier to understand.

Secondly, abbreviations in Russian can have several meanings, depending on the context. For example, the abbreviation "MO" can mean both "Ministry of Defense" and "Moscow Region". Therefore, it is important to consider the context and situation in order to correctly interpret the meaning of the abbreviation.

In addition, abbreviations in Russian can be both established and temporary. Established abbreviations are widely used and widely known, for example, "ВМФ" (Navy). Temporary abbreviations may be created for specific situations or events and may be less common [6, 24].

Thus, the peculiarities of the formation and functioning of abbreviations in the Russian language, using the example of military abbreviations, demonstrate the importance of their use in specialized vocabulary, as well as the need to take into account the context and situation for a correct understanding of the meaning of the abbreviation.

The peculiarities of the formation and functioning of abbreviations in the Uzbek language have their own pattern. In the Uzbek language, abbreviations are formed by shortening words or phrases. Typically, abbreviations use only the first letters of words, but other letters or symbols may also be used.

The functioning of abbreviations in the Uzbek language also has its own characteristics. Abbreviations are often used in writing, especially in official documents, scientific papers, and business correspondence. They help reduce the amount of text and make it easier to understand.

However, abbreviations are rarely used in spoken language because they can cause misunderstandings or hamper communication. Instead of abbreviations in oral speech, full words or phrases are more often used.

It is also worth noting that in the Uzbek language, abbreviations can be created not only on the basis of Uzbek words, but also on the basis of foreign words or phrases. This is due to the fact that in the Uzbek language there are many borrowed words from different languages.

In general, the features of the formation and functioning of abbreviations in the Uzbek language are associated with its specifics and context of use. Abbreviations help shorten text and make it easier to understand in writing, but their use in spoken language is limited.

Features of the formation and functioning of abbreviations in the Uzbek language, especially in the context of military abbreviations, are an interesting and important aspect of language learning. The Uzbek language, like many other languages, uses abbreviations to denote various terms and concepts, especially in the field of military affairs [1, 7].

One of the features of the formation of abbreviations in the Uzbek language is the use of abbreviations of words and expressions. Military abbreviations in the Uzbek language usually consist of the first letters of the words or expressions they represent. For example, the abbreviation "MV" means "Mudofaa vazirligi" (Ministry of Defense), and the abbreviation "MTT" means "Moddiy-texnik ta'minot" (logistics).

The functioning of abbreviations in the Uzbek language also has its own characteristics. Firstly, abbreviations in the Uzbek language are often used in official documents, military missions and other formal situations. They simplify and speed up the communication process, allowing information to be transmitted more compactly [7, 30].

Secondly, abbreviations in the Uzbek language can be used in colloquial speech, especially among military personnel and specialists in this field. They are part of specific terminology and help save time and effort when communicating.

In conclusion, the peculiarities of the formation and functioning of abbreviations in the Uzbek language, especially in the context of military abbreviations, reflect the specifics of the language and its use in various fields. Abbreviations in the Uzbek language allow you to convey information more compactly and efficiently, simplifying communication and making it easier to understand specific terminology.

CONCLUSION

It follows from this that the peculiarities of the formation and functioning of abbreviations in English, Russian and Uzbek languages, using the example of military abbreviations, represent an interesting topic for study. Military abbreviations are an important part of military terminology and are widely used in communication between military specialists.

In English, abbreviations are formed by reducing words or phrases to one or more letters. Military abbreviations in English usually consist of the first letters of words representing military terms or names of organizations. For example, NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization) - North Atlantic Treaty Organization, or UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) - Unmanned Aerial Vehicle. In English, abbreviations are often used in official documents and communications, making it easier and faster to exchange information.

In Russian, abbreviations are also formed by reducing words or phrases to one or more letters. However, in the Russian language, not only the abbreviation of the first letters of words is often used, but also the abbreviation of the middle or final letters. For example, the Strategic Missile Forces (Strategic Missile Forces) or the Navy (Navy). Russian abbreviations of military terms are often used in official documents, names of military units and military equipment.

In the Uzbek language, abbreviations are also formed by reducing words or phrases to one or more letters. However, in the Uzbek language, abbreviations are often used in communications between military specialists and in official documents. For example, HHM (Havo hujumidan mudofaa) - air defense. Uzbek abbreviations of military terms are also widely used in the names of military units and military equipment.

The formation and functioning of abbreviations of military terms in English, Russian and Uzbek languages have their own characteristics associated with the grammatical rules and traditions of each language. However, in all three languages, abbreviations play an important role in facilitating communication and reducing the amount of information. They are an integral part of military terminology and contribute to the more efficient functioning of military structures and organizations.

REFERENCES

1. Akhtambaev R.P. Features of speech culture in the work of military translators // Bulletin of Tomsk State University. – Tomsk, 2014. - No. 1 (13). – P.5-9.
2. Avasova I. Structural and semantic features of abbreviations. Current research journal of philological sciences, 3(10), 2022. p.59-66.
3. Avasova Irina. (2022). Specific Features of Using Abbreviation in English Military Discourse. *Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History*, 13, 22–26. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjpch/article/view/3022>
4. Avasova Irina. (2023). The Specificity of the functioning and translation of abbreviations in the English Military Discourse. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 20, 81-85. Retrieved from <https://www.scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbss/article/view/2356>
5. Bankevich V.V. On the question of the relationship between lexico-semantic and thematic groups // Semantics of words and sentences. - St. Petersburg, 2005. - With. 113-115.
6. Boyko M.G. Structural and semantic features of the formation of armored terminology in the English language: Abstract of thesis...cand.phil. Sci. – Omsk: OSU, 2011. – 24 p.
7. Ergasheva F.I. On the problem of abbreviation of English military vocabulary // Teaching of language and literature. – Tashkent, 2010, - No. 6. – P. 23-32.
8. Ergasheva F.I. Methods of formation of English military terms // Teaching of language and literature. – Tashkent, 2010. - No. 8. – P. 36-44.
9. Irina Rafailovna Avasova. (2023). Methods of translating English military abbreviations and acronyms into Russian and Uzbek languages. *Conferencea*, 45–47. Retrieved from <https://www.conferencea.org/index.php/conferences/article/view/2551>
10. Korovushkin, V.P. A short educational English-Russian and Russian-English minimum dictionary of American military jargon: V.P. Korovushkin. - Cherepovets, 1980. - 86 p.

11. Kurganov A. Military vocabulary in Turkic studies // Ilmiy munozara: muammo, echim va yutuk. - T.; 2019. – pp. 103-104.
12. Marchand H. The Categories and Types of Present-Day English Word-Formation. – Munchen: Ludicium, 1999. – 484 p.
13. Shermukhamedov Y., Umarov A. Russian-Uzbek dictionary of military terms. – T.: Fan, 1980. – 294 p.
1. 14.Sudzilovsky, G.A. Slang - what is it? English-Russian dictionary of military slang: G.A. Sudzilovsky. - M. : Military Publishing House, 1973. - 182 p.
14. Tatarinov V.A. General terminology. – M: Russian Philological Bulletin, 2006. – 526 p.
15. Wright S.E., Bading G.A. Handbook of Terminology Management. – Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing, 2001. – 549p.